

HALAL TOURISM CONCEPTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article provides information about halal tourism and services in Islamic tourism in case of Uzbekistan, and connection of religion with ancient and sacred places, and Muslim requirements for Muslim travelers.

Key words: halal tourism, tourism services, muslim requirements, historical places, shariah rules, halal concept.

In recent decades, the global expansion of the halal economy has had an impact on the financial industry and Islamic banking. However, it has an impact on tourism market activities. Halal tourism, previously known as the pilgrimage and umrah pilgrimage, is undergoing a paradigm shift. Religious purposes are no longer the core essence of halal tourism, rather, the trip process must be connected with Sharia rules.

The development of tourism is inclusive since non-Muslim travelers can take advantage of sharia-compliant services as well. Halal tourism include the presence of religious and pilgrimage sites as well as the provision of auxiliary services such halal food serving hotels and restaurants and spaces for prayer. As long as they do not go against sharia norms and values, tourist places and products in sharia tourism are the same as those in mainstream tourism. The potential for sharia tourism in Uzbekistan is enormous and can serve as a substitute for traditional travel, the packaging and branding are currently lacking the proper concepts.

Uzbekistan is very well known country to world tourism community for it's halal tourism . This nation, an ancient landmass in Central Asia, is known for its amazing exoticism, literature, and numerous stories. Like an unending desert with camel caravans passing in front of it, elegant towers, madrasas, tombs with oriental architecture, exquisite silk fabrics, exquisite gold embroidery, and a quaint landscape of mediaeval Islamic culture. There are a lot of religious places in Uzbekistan with full and interesting history. All built ancient places connected with religion. Because, during building of whole existed monument and historical places, Islam religion flourished high level at that time. Not only Cultural heritage tourism developed, also Religious tourism still developing and

rising with numbers of visits. Uzbekistan is rising in the Global Muslim Travel Index rankings as a result of its alluring tourism.

Halal Tourism is one of the systems of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan, created and designed specifically for Muslim tourists, the implementation of which continues to follow the principles of Sharia. The concept of halal has become a trend in the global economy, ranging from food, beverages, financial products and lifestyle products.

Many Muslim countries have started using this new concept as a new lifestyle trend. The global growth of the Muslim market is influenced by many things, namely the demographics of the young and large Muslim market. In addition, the rapid economic growth of Muslim majority countries, Islamic values promote the growth of Islamic business and lifestyle, the growth of international business transactions, the organization of Islamic conferences, the participation of international companies, technology and international connections.

According to the level of religious requirements, Muslim travelers can be divided into three groups:

1. Muslim travelers with strict religious requirements;
2. Muslim travelers with moderate religious requirements;
3. Muslim travelers with less religious requirements

Just as the religious requirements of Muslim travelers vary, so do the requirements for Muslim hospitality services.

A tourist destination that can be considered halal tourism is that it must meet the primary needs of Muslim tourists as cited by Crescent Rating. Focused on the development of Halal tourism, the company conducted surveys in 130 countries that show the six basic needs of Muslim tourists, namely:

- 1) Halal food (no alcohol, no pork, etc.).
- 2) Availability of rooms for worship.
- 3) Bathroom for washing with water.
- 4) Services during Ramadan such as iftar and sahur meals.
- 5) Adding non-halal labels if there are non-halal foods.
- 6) Privacy preserving entertainment options don't mix freely.

The charm of old buildings majestically situated in this city attracts travelers to come and return again and again. Samarkand is also an important city in the Islamic history of Central Asia. Some of the old buildings still stand strong as a testament to the Islamic past. For example, Imam al-

Bukhari, Imam al-Matrudi and other places. Even Imam al-Bukhari monument accepted second sacred place in Islam religion for visit after Hajj.

The tomb complex of Imam Al Bukhari is located near Samarkand. The architectural composition of this complex uses traditions and national architecture. The unified complex consists of a tomb, a mosque, an administrative office, and several other buildings built around and around a courtyard. The tomb of Imam Al Bukhari is located in the center of the complex. It is a cube shaped building covered by a 17-meter high dome. The door to the right of the tomb leads to the lady. Which is a place of worship and continues down. The theologian and the tomb on stilts are covered with marble. The mosque is located on the left side of the courtyard, where approximately 1500 Muslims can pray. The walls of the building are decorated with bright green, blue and white tiles as well as marble, onyx and granite. The same on the floor, which received many decorations. The interior of the dome is covered with bright decorative patterns.

Uzbekistan has been named the favorite destination of 2020 by the travel website Lonely Planet. Uzbekistan entered to the list of travel website Lonely Planet as a favourite destination for travel. Uzbekistan ranks Top 10 place which halal tourism developed. One of the benefit of country is in tourism infrastructure paying attention to show halal tourism services to all service system. This is preferable choice for visitors and important way of attracting Muslim traveler to this country.

Uzbekistan is a country located in Central Asia that has unique halal tourism or pilgrimage tourism because of the many graves of great Muslim scholars in Uzbekitan such as Imam Bukhari or Ibn Sina. In its tourism development, Uzbekistan is quite successful. This is evidenced by an increase in the ranking of halal tourism in GMTI

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